

Decolonizing Digital Preservation and Access: Case Studies from a Canadian University Archives and Library

We acknowledge and respect the Łkʷłkʷłkn (Songhees and Xʷsepškm/Esquimalt) Peoples on whose territory the university stands, and the Łkʷłkʷłkn and W̱SÁNEĆ Peoples whose historical relationships with the land continue to this day.

Neil J. Sterritt Archives

Special Collections and University Archives are acting as stewards of the Neil J. Sterritt archives. Sterritt, a member of the Gitksan Nation and President of the Gitksan-Wet'suwet'en Tribal Council from 1981-87, played a key role in the major land title case *Delgamuukw v. British Columbia*. The material in his archives includes cultural knowledge restricted to Gitksan citizens under family laws. SCUA has a stewardship agreement with the Sterritt family under which access is restricted and may be granted according to the collective ownership of each Gitksan House under Gitksan Law. Therefore the preservation packaging in Archivematica of born-digital and digitized materials – for repatriation and future access – is guided by this granular level of restrictions.

Administered by the First Nations Information Governance Council, OCAP® are the principles of **Ownership, Control, Access, and Possession** that guide our management of Indigenous archives.

Nancy J. Turner Archives

Dr. Nancy Turner is a settler ethnobotanist who has worked primarily with First Nations in B.C. from the 1960s to the current day. Canadian copyright legislation has not caught up with traditional knowledge rights and Indigenous data sovereignty; we attempt to address those through our donation agreement and outreach to Nations. Preservation packaging decisions are guided by at minimum the Nation-level for choice of preservation system and process; access controls are determined by Nations as the primary rights-holders; data sovereignty was considered when choosing a digitization vendor.

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Canadian context

The Truth and Reconciliation of Canada (TRC) issued its final report in 2015. The TRC was established in 2008 with the mandate to document and expose the vast harms of Canada's Indian Residential School system. The TRC heard and documented school survivor and witness statements across the country and collected copies of church and government records which are housed at the National Centre for Truth and Reconciliation in Winnipeg, Manitoba. The TRC issued 94 Calls to Action directed to government and society; call #70 was directed to the archival community. How do these calls to action affect the work of librarians and archivists working in the digital preservation sphere?

Campus context

UVic's campus was established in 1961 and is superimposed upon the homelands of Lekwungen- and SENĆOŦEN-speaking communities. While these are treaty lands, such agreements have not held up to their original spirit. Despite increasing efforts to decolonize and Indigenize, UVic remains a deeply colonial institution in name and structure. Reckoning with this problematic legacy is ongoing work for archivists and librarians working directly with patrons and records at the junction of where colonial histories and contemporary truth-telling initiatives converge. We remain committed to improving relationships with our Indigenous friends and colleagues and thank them for their patience and wisdom.

Indigenous Language Revitalization

UVic is internationally renowned for Indigenous language revitalization (ILR). As this subject's librarian for a decade, Pia develops collections for students, faculty, and community members excelling in this revitalization research. Through robust acquisitions budgets, highly curated collections, and course-integrated library instruction, UVic Libraries' ILR collection has closely mirrored an increasingly successful academic program. In addition to ILR library guides that are used by 1K+ a year (libguides.uvic.ca/indigenouseducation), Pia also teaches a for-credit, graduate-level course titled 'IED594: The Research Proposal and Literature Review' with an accompanying 68-page OER resource workbook: hdl.handle.net/1828/22653. This embedded librarianship ensures cultural humility and cultural safety, particularly for remote access to language materials.

Supporting Indigenous studies

Serving as a non-Indigenous librarian supporting students studying Indigenous Studies (IS) programs presents a unique challenge for respectful access. While many IS students self-identify as Indigenous, the majority are non-Indigenous, studying IS as a minor to complement other programs. What brings many to the program is an interest in so-called 'helping,' but such aspirations have historically resulted in profoundly problematic impacts. Navigating the contested terrain of both recommending scholarly-quality resources, while also informally bringing awareness to students of the broader social and political legacies of settler colonialism requires both tact and expertise. Such research consultations serve as impactful initiating interactions for the students, but also resulted in unanticipated emotional labour within a professional setting.

Photo credits: All photographs were taken by Pia Russell and reflect engagement in locally-specific cultural activities. The forest is Mystic Vale. The lower border is woven cedar from STO:LO homelands near Chilliwack.